

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT WEED MANAGEMENT METHODS ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF KENAF (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) IN NIGERIAN SAVANNAH

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the research work was to determine the Economic Analysis of Different Weed Management Methods on the Growth and Yield of Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) in Nigerian Savannah. The two field trials were conducted during the 2017 wet season at the research farm of the Institute for Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University, Samaru, Zaria (Lat. 11° 11' N, Long. 07° 38'E) 686m above sea level and experimental research farm of College of Animal Science, Division of Agriculture College, Ahmadu Bello University, Mando Campus, Kaduna (Lat. 7° 26' N and Long. 10° 31' E) 576m above sea level both in northern guinea savannah ecological zone of Nigeria. The treatments consisted of five weed control methods, which included three pre-emergence herbicides (Pendimethalin at 2.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹, S-Metolachor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ and Tank mixture of Pendimethalin, and S-Metolachor at 1.0 + 0.5kg a.i ha⁻¹, hoe weeding at 3 and 6 weeks after sowing (WAS) and an unweeded check. The treatments were factorially combined and laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and replicated three times. The results from the study revealed that among the weed control management methods evaluated, the application of S- Metolachor at 1.0kg a.i ha⁻¹ gave the highest economic returns with lower weed cover score and weed dry weight which was comparable to the hoe weeding that gave the least returns compared to other herbicides treatments and parameters such as weed cover score, weed dry weight and weed control efficiency while crop injury was higher in the unweeded check treatment. The hoe weeded resulted in the highest crop vigour and significantly increased growth parameters rate such as plant height, crop growth, and relative growth rate but was not economically efficient compared to herbicide treatments.

Keywords: kenaf, economic analysis, cost benefit, pre-emergence herbicides and yield.

INTRODUCTION

Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) is a member of the hibiscus family (Malvaceae) that is a fibre crop of tropical origin indigenous to Africa. The rise in price coupled with Government determination to reduce the country's dependence on imports have resulted in the major interest of stimulating domestic production. Federal government of Nigeria's strategy since the 1960s has been to fund research on kenaf and also to disseminate

proven research findings on the farmers and encourage mass production. Although kenaf has been traditionally grown by Nigerian farmers, local production has been confined to a large extent to home-stead gardens across the country Lee *et al.* (2021). The kenaf fibres are of better quality than the core fibres; both, however, can be utilized in various blends for the production of pulp. Xu *et al.*(2020). Kenaf seed can be used for vegetable oil extraction, its oil is odorless,

$$\text{Weed control efficiency (WCE)} = \frac{WDC - WDT}{WDC}$$

Where, WDC were the weed density (number/m²) in control plot

WDT were the weed density (number/m²) in treated plot.

Plants were harvested from the net row of each plot at 12 WAS. The stems was carefully peeled and retted and the fibre strands were removed. The fibre strands were oven-dried and weighted, and the yield of ribbon and fibre per plant and hectare were determined.

Data collected were subjected to Statistical Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and using model procedure of statistical analysis system (SAS) software version 8. Means were separated using the least significant different (LSD) at 5% of probability (Rangaswamy, 2010). The following are the basic parameters used in determined the economic analysis of different methods of weed control in the research trials.

(A) Total yield of fibre (Kg/ha) = Quantity of fibre produced per hectare

(B) Total income of Kenaf fibre (₦/ha) = Total Yield of fibre (Kg/ha) x Price/Kg

(C) Total cost of production (₦/ha) = Cost of weed control + Cost of labour

(D) Net Benefit (₦/ha) = Total Income – Total cost of production

(E) Benefit of weed control (₦/ha) = Net Benefit of weed control – Total income of weedy check

$$\text{(F) Cost: Benefit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Benefit of weed control treatment}}{\text{Total cost of production}}$$

$$\text{(G) Return on Investment (₦/ha)} = \frac{\text{Total Income of each treatment}}{\text{Total cost of production}}$$

RESULTS

Table 1 shows weeds sample collected at the experimental sites (Samaru and Kaduna). Weeds sample collected at 6 and 9 weeks after sowing (WAS) from the experimental sites (Samaru and Kaduna) were identified and classified into grasses, broadleaves and sedges. The most dominant weed species of the grass family at Samaru experimental site, were *Cynodon dactylon* (L), pers, *Digitaria horizontalis* Wild and *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* (Clayton) with high level of incidence, *Eragrostis atravirens* (Dest) Trin and *Sida acuta* had moderate level of incidence, while *Chloris pjllosa* Schumachs and *Panicum masimum* jacq had low incidence, Only *Euphorbia heterophylla* was broadleaf with high level weed incidence, *Boerhavia diffusa* Linn and *Commellina benghalensis* had moderate incidence,

Cyperus rotuntadus Linn was only sedge with high level of incidence and *Cyperus esculentus* Linn was the only sedge species with moderate incidence At Kaduna experimental site, *Cynodon dactylon* (L), pers, *Panicum maximum* Jacq, *Rottboellia cochinchinensis* (Clayton) and *Sida acuta* were grasses weed with high level of incidence *Chloris pjllosa* Schumachs and *Digitaria horizontalis* Wild had moderate level of infestation and *Eragrostis atravirens* (Dest) Trin had low incidence. *Commellina benghalensis* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* were broadleaf with high level weed incidence, while *Acanthospermum hispidium* D C and *Boerhavia diffusa* had low incidence. *Cyperus esculentus* Linn was the only sedge species with high incidence *Cyperus rotundus* Linn. had low incidence (Table 1).

Table 1. List of weed species observed at Samaru and Kaduna experimental sites in 2017 wet season

Types of weeds	Family	Samaru Level on incidence	Kaduna
Grasses			
<i>Chloris pjllosa</i> Schumachs	Poaceae	+	++
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L), Pers	Poaceae	+++	+++
<i>Digitaria horizonfialis</i> Wild	Poaceae	+++	++
<i>Panicum maximum</i> Jacq	Poaceae	+	+++
<i>Eragrostis atravirens</i> (Dest) Trin	Poaceae	++	+
<i>Rottboellia cochinchinensis</i> (Clayton)	Poaceae	+++	+++
<i>Sida acuta</i>	Poaceae	++	+++
Broadleaves			
<i>Acanthospermum hispidium</i> D C	Asteriaceae	++	++
<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i>	Asteriaceae	++	++
<i>Commellina benghalensis</i>	Commelinaceae	++	+++
<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Euphorbiaceae	+++	+++
Sedges			
<i>Cyperus esculentus</i> Linn	Cyperaceae	++	+++
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn	Cyperaceae	+++	++
Key			
+	Low incidence		
++	Moderate incidence		
+++	High incidence		

Weed cover score

Weed cover score as influenced by weed control methods in kenaf at various sampling weeks at Samaru and Kaduna is presented in Table 2. The results were consistent in both locations, at 3 and 6 WAS, the weedy check recorded significantly higher weed cover score compared with all other treatments. Among the herbicides, application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 Kg a.i ha⁻¹ resulted in significantly lower weed cover score follow by Pendimethalin at 2.0 Kg a.i ha⁻¹. Weed cover score influenced by the hoe-weeded control treatment performed better but not comparable to that influenced by S-Metolachlor at 1.0 Kg a.i ha⁻¹ on the basis of cost benefit analysis.

The effect of NPK fertilization on weed cover was significant at all the sampling weeks at both locations. At Samaru in all the sampling weeks, weed cover score significantly increased with each increase in NPK fertilizer rate from zero to 90:45:45 kg ha⁻¹ except at 6 WAS, where zero and 30 :15:15 kg NPK ha⁻¹ recorded statistically similar weed cover score . Highest weed cover score was observed at 90:45:45 kg NPK ha⁻¹ rate. At Kaduna location, similar response of weed cover score was observed except at 9 WAS where 60:30:30 and 90:45:45 kg NPK ha⁻¹ recorded statistically similar weed cover score. (Table 2)

Table 2: Effect of weed management methods and NPK fertilization on weed cover score of kenaf in Samaru and Kaduna during 2017 wet season

Treatments	Weed Cover Score ³		Weed Cover Score 6WAS	
	<u>3WAS²</u>			
	Samaru	Kaduna	Samaru	Kaduna
Weed Control Methods (W)				
Pendimethalin 2.0 Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	2.37c ¹	2.50c	3.33c	3.18c
S-Metolachlor 1.0 Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	2.26d	2.41d	3.12d	3.08d
Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor (1.0+0.5) Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	2.50b	2.63d	3.48b	3.37b
Hoe weeding (3 and 6 WAS)	2.17e	2.23e	3.00e	2.67e
Weedy check	2.83a	2.75a	3.67a	3.75a
S.E (±)	0.058	0.051	0.055	0.056
Fertilizer Rate (Kg NPK ha ⁻¹) (F)				
0:0:0	2.27d	2.10d	3.00c	3. lid
30:15:15	2.40c	2.34c	3.00c	3.13c
60:30:30	2.47b	2.40b	3.07b	3.19b
90:45:45	2.60a	2.53a	3.33a	3.27a
S.E (±)	0.047	0.041	0.044	0.045
Interaction				
W x F	NS ⁴	NS	NS	NS

¹Means followed by the same letter within the same treatment group are statistically the same using **DMRT** at 5% Level of significance. ²WAS —Week after sowing
³Weed cover score using scale of 1-9 where 1= least weedy plot and 9= most weedy plot ⁴NS - Not Significant.

Weed control efficiency

Weed control efficiency as affected by weed control methods and NPK fertilization in kenaf at various sampling weeks at Samaru and Kaduna is presented in Table 3. The results which are consistent at both locations showed that in all the sampling weeks, the hoe weeded control recorded significantly higher weed control efficiency compared to all other weed control treatments. Among the herbicide treatments application of S- Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ gave a better weed control efficiency compared to the application of Pendimethalin at 2.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ and tank mixture of Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor at

1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i ha⁻¹. The application of Pendimethalin at 2.0 Kg a.i ha⁻¹ had higher weed control efficiency than treated plots with application of tank mixture of Pendimethalin + S- Metolachlor at 1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i ha⁻¹. The weedy check treatments consistently resulted in lowest weed control efficiency at both locations.

The effect of NPK fertilization on weed control efficiency at the sampling weeks at both locations indicated that application of 90:45:45kg NPKha⁻¹ resulted to significantly higher weed control efficiency compared to other rates of NPK application at both locations (Table 3).

Table 3: Effect of weed management methods and NPK fertilization on weed control efficiency of kenaf in Samaru and Kaduna during 2017 wet season

Treatments Weed	Weed Control Efficiency		Weed Control Efficiency	
	6WAS ²		9WAS	
	Samaru	Kaduna	Samaru	Kaduna
Control Methods (W)				
Pendimethalin 2.0 Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	65.41c ¹	60.25c	62.19c	55.24c
S-Metolachlor 1.0 Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	71.83b	66.13b	68.11b	64.49b
Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor (1.0+0.5) Kg a.i ha ⁻¹	55.35d	54.81d	52.11d	50.11d
Hoe weeding (3 and 6 WAS)	83.25a	79.66a	78.95a	76.54a
Weedy check	0.00e	0.00e	0.00d	0.00d
S.E(±)	0.242	0.215	0.203	0.198
Fertilizer Rate (Kg NPK ha ⁻¹) (F)				
0:0:0	0.00d	0.00d	0.00d	0.00d
30:15:15	17.27c	16.30c	18.65c	17.68c
60:30:30	25.76b	24.27b	27.07b	22.78b
90:45:45	33.33a	32.97a	35.53a	34.87a
S.E (±) Interaction	0.193	0.172	0.162	0.159
W x F	NS ³	NS	NS	NS

¹Means followed by the same letter within the same treatment group are statistically the same using **DMRT** at 5% Level of significance. ²WAS -Week after sowing ³NS - Not Significant

Ribbon Yield per hectare (kg ha⁻¹)

Ribbon yield per hectare in kenaf as influenced by weed control methods and NPK fertilization of kenaf at Samaru and Kaduna is presented in Table 4. The result at both locations showed that among the weed control methods, the hoe weeded control produced higher ribbon yield per hectare compared to other methods. Among the herbicide treatments, application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ produced higher ribbon yield per hectare compared with others. Weedy check

plots consistently produced crops with lower ribbon yield per hectare at both locations. The effect on NPK fertilization with respect to ribbon yield per hectare at both locations showed that application of 90:45:45kg NPK ha⁻¹ significantly had higher ribbon yield per hectare compared with other rates of NPK applied. To every increase in NPK rate from zero to 90:45:45kg NPKha⁻¹ there was a significant increase in ribbon yield per hectare at both locations (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of weed management methods and NPK fertilization on Ribbon yield per plant and per hectre of kenaf in Samaru and Kaduna during 2017 wet season

Treatments	Ribbon Yield/Plant (g)		Ribbon Yield kg ha^{-1}	
	Samaru	Kaduna	Samaru	Kaduna
Weed Control Methods (W)				
Pendimethalin 2.0 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$	28.69c $^{-1}$	26.58b	62.22c	57.52c
S-Metolachlor 1.0 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$	32.73a	28.42a	66.66b	62.22b
Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor (1.0 + 0.5) kg a.i ha $^{-1}$	20.48d	19.94c	44.44d	40.64c
Hoe weeding (3&6 WAS)	30.19b	28.83a	71.11a	66.45a
Weedy check	18.42e	16.26d	40.00e	35.56d
S.E (\pm)	0.014	0.008	0.014	0.008
Fertilizer Rate (kgNPK ha$^{-1}$) (F)				
0:0:0	20.84d	18.52d	46.28d	43.97d
30:15:15	24.74c	22.74	53.33c	48.89b
60:30:30	26.67c	28.25b	57.55b	52.45c
90:45:45	36.81a	30.67a	80.00a	69.12a
S.E (\pm)	0.011	0.006	0.011	0.006
Interaction				
WxF	NS ³	NS	NS	NS

¹Means followed by the same letter within the same treatment group are statistically the same using **DMRT** at 5% Level of Significance. ²**WAS** – Week after sowing. ³**NS** – Not Significant

Fibre Yield per Hectare (kg ha $^{-1}$)

Plants were harvested from the net row of each plot at 12 WAS. The stems was carefully peeled and retted and the fibre strands were removed. The fibre strands were oven-dried and weighted, and the yield per plant and hectare were determined. Fibre yield per hectare in kenaf as influenced by weed control methods and NPK fertilization on kenaf at Samaru and Kaduna is presented in Table 5. At Samaru location, the result showed that among the weed control methods, the hoe weeded control produced significantly higher fibre yield per hectare but was statistically similar to that produced by the application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$. The application of tank mixture of Pendimethalin + S- Metolachlor at 1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$ produced lower fibre yield per hectare but comparable to the fibre yield produced by the

weedy check. At Kaduna location, the hoe weeded control resulted in significantly higher fibre yield per hectare but was at par with the application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$. The application of Pendimethalin at 2.0 Kg a.i ha $^{-1}$ produced higher fibre yield per hectare than the application of tank mixture of Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor at 1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i ha $^{-1}$ while weedy check that produced crops with lesser fibre yield per hectare. The effect of NPK fertilization with on fibre yield per hectare at both locations showed that application of 90:45:45kg NPKha $^{-1}$ resulted in significantly higher fibre yield per hectare compared to other rates of NPK applied. Each increase in NPK rate from 0 to 90:45:45kg NPKha $^{-1}$ gave a significant increase in fibre yield per hectare at both locations (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of weed management methods and NPK fertilization on Fibre Yield per Plant (g) and per hectare (kg) of kenaf in Samaru and Kaduna during 2017 wet season

Treatments	Fibre Yield / Plant (g)		Fibre Yield kgha ⁻¹	
	Samaru	Kaduna	Samaru	Kaduna
Weed Control Methods (W)				
Pendimethalin 2.0 kg a.i ha ⁻¹	19.98c ¹	14.82b	845.37 ¹	638.30b
S-Metolachlor 1.0 kg a.i ha ⁻¹	20.76b	19.78a	851.16a	744.68a
Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor (1.0 + 0.5) kg a.i ha ⁻¹	12.74d	12.17c	531.91b	433.67c
Hoe weeding (3&6 WAS)	21.54a	19.85a	866.89a	754.125a
Weedy check	10.56e	9.67d	527.78b	425.53c
S.E (±)	0.014	0.008	0.006	0.005
Fertilizer Rate (kgNPK ha⁻¹) (F)				
0:0:0	10.96d	10.06	537.91d	446.23d
30:15:15	12.46c	11.48b	638.30c	565.98c
60:30:30	14.54b	13.99c	734.65b	675.76c
90:45:45	19.45a	17.49a	989.01a	858.44a
S.E (±)	0.011	0.006	0.005	0.004
Interaction				
WxF	NS ³	NS	NS	NS

¹Means followed by the same letter within the same treatment group are statistically the same using **DMRT** at 5% Level of Significance. ²WAS – Week after sowing. ³NS

Economic Analysis

Cost Benefit Ratio

It is an indication of relative economic performance of the treatments. A ratio of one indicates the venture is neither making profit nor loss, it is breaking even, while a ratio of less than one means a loss, but a ratio of more than one indicates a profit and the economic

viability of the treatment compared with the control treatment. As shown in Tables 6 and 7, Cost Benefit Ratio of different methods of weed management indicated that the application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ is most economic viable compared to other methods of weed management employed in both locations.

Table 6: Cost: Benefit analysis of weed control on Kenaf with pre emergence herbicides and hoe weeding in Samaru during 2017 wet season.

Variables	Weed Control Treatments				
	Pend (P)	Meta (M)	Pend + Meta	Hoe weeding	Weedy check
(A) Total yield of Kenaf fibre (Kg/ha)	545.4	851.2	531.3	866.9	527.8
(B) Total income of fibre (₦/ha)	109080	170240	106260	173380	105560
(C) Cost of weed control (₦/ha)	6000	8000	7000	37037	0.00
(D) Cost of labour	2000	2000	2000	2000	0.00
(E) Total cost of production (C+D)	8000	10000	9000	39037	0.00
(F) Net Benefit (₦/ha) (B-E)	101080	160240	97260	134343	105560
(G) Benefit over untreated control (₦/ha)	-4480	54680	-8300	28783	-
(H) Cost: Benefit ratio (G/E)	1: -0.56	1: 5.47	1: -0.92	1: 0.74	-
ROI(B/E)	13.64	17.02	11.81	4.44	-

ROI indicate return on investment.

Table 7: Cost: Benefit analysis of weed control on Kenaf with pre- emergence herbicides and hoe weeding in Kaduna during 2017 wet season.

Variables	Weed Control Treatments				
	Pend (P)	Meta (M)	Pend + Meta	Hoe weeding	Weedy check
(A) Total yield of Kenaf fibre (Kg/ha)	638.3	744.7	433.7	754.1	425.5
(B) Total income of fibre (₦/ha)	127660	148940	86740	150820	85100
(C) Cost of weed control (₦/ha)	6000	8000	7000	37037	0.00
(D) Cost of labour	2000	2000	2000	2000	0.00
(E) Total cost of production (C+D)	8000	10000	9000	39037	0.00
(F) Net Benefit (₦/ha) (B-E)	119660	138940	77740	111783	85100
(G) Benefit over untreated control (₦/ha)	34560	53840	-7360	26683	-
(H) Cost: Benefit ratio (G/E)	1: 4.32	1: 5.38	1: -0.82	1: 2.86	-
ROI (B/E)	15.96	14.89	9.64	3.86	-

ROI indicate return on investment.

Return on Investment

It shows the returns to capital investment over production period, that is, a measure of profitability of the investment capital. It also reflects true value of profit or gain that can be realized for every ₦1 investment made on business. The ratio not only indicates substantial return to enterprise, but also a high level efficiency in the use of capital. As shown

in Tables 8, Return on Investment after the used of different methods of weed management to suppressed weeds growth during the trials indicated that the application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ gave highest Return on Investment compared to other methods of weed management used in both locations

Table 8: Cost and Benefit analysis of weed control on Kenaf with pre- emergence herbicides and hoe weeding at Samaru and Kaduna during 2017 wet season.

Variables	Weed Control Treatments				
	Pend (P)	Meta (M)	Pend + Meta	Hoe weeding	Weedy check
(A) Total yield of Kenaf fibre (Kg/ha)	591.9	798.0	482.5	810.5	476.7
(B) Total income of fibre (₦/ha)	118380	159600	96500	162100	95340
(C) Cost of weed control (₦/ha)	6000	8000	7000	37037	0.00
(D) Cost of labour	2000	2000	2000	2000	0.00
(E) Total cost of production (C+D)	8000	10000	9000	39037	0.00
(F) Net Benefit (₦/ha) (B-E)	110380	149600	87500	123063	95340
(G) Benefit over untreated control (₦/ha)	15040	54260	-7840	27723	-
(H) Cost: Benefit ratio (G/E)	1: 1.88	1: 5.43	1: -0.87	1: 0.71	-
ROI (B/E)	14.80	15.96	10.72	4.15	-

ROI indicate return on investment

Discussion

Effective weed control is essential for kenaf growth and optimum productivity; the critical period for weed control in kenaf is during the period of crop establishment. (Das, 2008). Pre- emergence herbicides such as S-Metolachlor and Pendimethalin are some of the effective herbicides for weed management in kenaf production. (Othman *et al.* 2006). Among the weed management methods, application of S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹

resulted in most economic viable option with respect to cost benefit ratio and return on investment compared to the hoe- weeded control treatments that performed outstanding with respect to suppression of weed growth but however these control method was not economic viable, this verified the report by Webber, C. L. III (1992) that S-Metolachlor is a good weeds growth inhibitor. Pendimethalin herbicide was only effective in controlling weeds of grasses families but performed poor

in broadleaves weeds, this was manifested by its lower weed control efficiency, high weed cover and lower yields compared to the later. The application of tank mixture of Pendimethalin + S-Metolachlor at 1.0 + 0.5 kg a.i ha⁻¹ gave lower weed control efficiency, high weed cover and lower yields but better than the weedy check control treatments. Vencill *et al.* (2002) reported that the mixture of Pendimethalin and S-Metolachlor herbicides will reduced the efficacy of the herbicides due to the antagonistic effect of their chemical composition rather than synergic effect and in turned result to poor weed control as shown in weed control efficiency, yields and economic efficient. Kenaf crops in the treatments where

90:45:45kg ha⁻¹ NPK was applied observed to produced higher yield than the other treatments during the period when the trial was conducted. The report justified the earlier works of Hassan *et al.* (2018) that higher yield of kenaf was attributed to higher rate of NPK application.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that the use of chemical herbicides especially S-Metolachlor at 1.0 kg a.i ha⁻¹ was effective in kenaf weed management at reduced cost and higher return on investment and further work might be carried out in the field for confirmation.

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